

Studies on chloranil + benzoic acid complexes and chloranil + salicylic acid complexes in mixed solvents

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In order to understand the differential behaviour of the solvents on the stability of the molecular complexes, the association constants between chloranil and benzoic acid, salicylic acid have been determined in C₆H₆ + *n*-C₆H₁₄ mixtures (0–100%). The values change marginally with solvent composition and no positive correlation could be made.

The forces responsible for the formation of different types of addition complexes have not been fully understood. Apart from the strong interactions, different types of weak interactions play a vital role in the formation of stable complexes and are particularly important in understanding the mechanism of drug-receptor interactions¹. The interactions as such are weak but the combination of such forces make the addition complexes fairly stable though it is difficult to understand the nature of the forces and their individual contributions to the formation of the complexes. The complex formed between quinones and benzene have been shown to be dipolar or π - π CT complexes². Naturally, benzoic acid and salicylic acid having the skeleton of benzene ring have the possibility of forming molecular complex with quinone. This had been experimentally verified and CT complex formation between chloranil and benzoic acids in CHCl₃ and C₆H₆ had been reported⁵. However, it had been pointed out that the possibility of H-bonding can not be ruled out in these cases. Examples of cooperative charge-transfer and H-bonding interactions have been known^{4,5}.

Drug-receptor interactions involve a large number of competitive weak interactions, CT interaction is one of them. Examples of pure CT interactions are rare. Moreover, the behaviour of solvents can not be defined by a singular solvent property. Naturally, all correlations of spectral solvent shifts, solvent effect on EDA, H-bonding or other complexes with some specific solvent parameter are of limited utility. Moreover, microscopic and macroscopic properties of the solvents are entirely different. Studies of spectral parameters and association constants in different binary mixtures may be of importance to comprehend the nature of interactions and the differential behaviour of solvents in a better way.

These consideration led us to study the spectral solvent shifts and changes in the association constants between chloranil and benzoic/salicylic acids in benzene + *n*-hexane mixtures.

Results and Discussion

Complex formation between chloranil and benzoic acid had been determined to be 1 : 1 by Job's method of continuous variation. For the reaction, D + A $\rightleftharpoons$ DA (D = benzoic or salicylic acid) and A = chloranil), the equilibrium constant (K_C) can be written as

$$K_C = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \times \frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \gamma_A} \approx \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \quad (1)$$

Since D and A are taken in equivalent proportions, an iterative procedure utilising the equation,

$$\frac{C_1}{(d_2-d_1)l} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2-\epsilon_1)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2-\epsilon_1)(C_2-x)l} \frac{1}{k} \quad (2)$$

were used to calculate K in the way described in our previous communication^{3,6}. Consistency of the result also suggest 1 : 1 complex formation. The results are presented in Table 1. According to Foster⁵, K values obtained from optical data give best results when equivalent concentrations of D and A are used. Our results can thus be regarded to be accurate and reliable.

Benzoic acid and salicylic acid are molecules of biological importance. Quinones like chloranils have also biological importance. The compounds have (i) benzene ring where electron densities are modified by substituents, (ii) hydrogen bonding capabilities, (iii) dipole moments. Naturally, spectral solvent shifts of the components are dependent on a number of factors like dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole, dispersion interactions etc. which may reinforce and cancel each other. In addition to the forces al-

ready described, charge-transfer and hydrogen bonding interactions are likely to take place when chloranil is mixed with benzoic acid or substituted acids. Under these conditions, no appreciable change in the spectral shift was noted though considerable changes in optical density were observed

due to solvent dipoles, interaction between permanent solute and solvent dipoles etc.⁷.

It is desirable to have more work in this direction to get useful conclusions.

Experimental

Chloranil, benzoic acid and salicylic acid were of guaranteed quality (E Merck or B.D.H.) and used as such. Benzene and *n*-hexane were of spectroscopic grade (E Merck and S.R.L., India). Solvents were mixed in different proportions to get the mixtures.

The composition of the complex between chloranil and benzoic acid was determined using Job's method of continuous variation by measuring the absorbances of equimolar solutions of chloranil and benzoic acid in varying proportions and the corresponding blanks containing chloranil only.

Different concentrations of the components were mixed in the 1 : 1 proportions and allowed to come to equilibrium. The absorption measurements were made with a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer controlled at 298 K using freshly prepared solutions. All the components and the complexes strongly absorbed in the 200–350 nm region. Naturally, the determination of conspicuous charge transfer bands in this region is difficult. To avoid complications, the complexes were studied in range 370–375 nm, where absorption due to acids may be eliminated, and the absorption in the region were due to the complexes and chloranil.

Table 1. Equilibrium constants (K_{DA}) and free energy changes (ΔG^0) of donor-acceptor complexes in mixed solvent at 298 K

Acceptor: Chloranil, density of benzene = 0.877 g ml⁻¹, λ_{max} = 336 nm, *n*-hexane = 0.658 g ml⁻¹

Sl no	Mixed solvent		Donor benzoic acid		Donor salicylic acid	
	<i>n</i> -hexane	benzene	10 ⁻² K_{DA} dm ³ mol ⁻¹	- ΔG^0 kJ mol ⁻¹	10 ⁻² K_{DA} dm ³ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^0 kJ mol ⁻¹
1	0	100	2.31	13.48	1.44	12.31
2	10	90	2.44	13.62	2.06	13.20
3	20	80	1.24	11.94	2.08	13.22
4	30	70	2.46	13.64	2.04	13.18
5	40	60	2.51	13.69	2.06	13.20
6	50	50	2.65	13.82	2.41	13.59
7	60	40	1.54	12.48	2.14	13.29
8	70	30	2.08	13.22	1.99	13.11
9	80	20	2.46	13.64	1.86	12.95
10	90	10	2.38	13.56	1.82	12.89
11	100	0	2.35	13.52	1.74	12.78

The association constants of the chloranil + benzoic acid complexes have been found to be usually higher than those of chloranil + salicylic acid complexes. It is very difficult to correlate the data with any physical property. However, it has been found that the values are nearly constant, and a change has been observed in the 40–60% *n*-hexane + benzene mixtures.

The results appear to be rational in view of the fact that both benzene and *n*-hexane are non-polar and have almost similar dielectric constant values (ϵ_{20} benzene = 2.284 and ϵ_{20} *n*-hexane = 1.890) though indices of refraction [$^nD_{25}$ *n*-hexane = 1.372 and $^nD_{25}$ benzene = 1.498] are slightly different. Naturally, differential behaviour of the spectral solvent shifts of solutes and the complexes with solvents can hardly be expected. Binary mixtures of solvents having different polarities or dielectric constants and refractive indices may provide better insight regarding different type of interactions like dispersion effects (accounting for the effects of non-polar solvents on non-polar solutes), the interaction of the solute permanent dipole with the solute in-

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